

Supplementary material of "Investigating vividness bias in language models through art interpretations (Jul 2024)"

- 1) **Persona creation:** this document outlines the creation of detailed personas used in the preliminary investigation. Each persona is characterized by specific demographics and background information to provide the LLM with diverse perspectives for generating art interpretations.
- 2) **Bard Berry Dress Checked:** this document contains detailed interpretations of the "Berry Dress" artwork conducted in the earlier experiment¹, before Bard update. It includes multiple prompts and responses to understand how different personas affect the interpretation of the artwork. The interpretations highlight various themes from the art interpretation and also notes inconsistencies and errors in Bard's responses.
- 3) **Bard La Reunion Checked:** this document details Bard's interpretation of the "La Reunion" artwork by Zanele Muholi. The document highlights several iterations of prompts and responses, showing Bard's initial misunderstanding of the image. The interpretations highlight various themes from the art interpretation. The document also points out Bard's limitations in accurately recognizing and describing the image from the provided link.
- 4) **Bard Margaret Thatcher Checked:** this document contains Bard's interpretations of "Margaret Thatcher's Lunch" by Derek Jarman. The responses explore various themes such as political critique, the impact of Thatcher's policies on different communities, and personal reflections based on the personas. Bard's responses include detailed symbolic interpretations of the elements in the artwork and also Bard's inability to view images directly and the challenges this poses for accurate interpretation.
- 5) **Bard Miss Muffet Checked:** this document details Bard's interpretations of the "Miss Muffet" artwork. It includes multiple iterations of prompts and responses, showing Bard's initial focus on the nursery rhyme rather than the artwork itself. It also explores how different personas influence the interpretation, with relevant section highlighted.
- 6) **Results Part A Document:** this document presents the initial findings from the earlier experiment. It includes detailed descriptions of the AI's performance and its limitations: misunderstanding of artworks, incorrect source information, tool limitations and Persona-Specific Interpretations. This part highlights the initial challenges and inaccuracies encountered using Bard for art interpretation.
- 7) **Results Part B Document:** this document presents the initial findings from the earlier experiment conducted again after Bard update. It includes detailed descriptions of the AI's performance and its limitations: misunderstanding of artworks, incorrect source information,

¹ All the Bard interpretations are highlighted under four categories: **Misunderstanding**, **Source Information**, **LLM Tool Limitations** and **Personas' Diversity Features**.

tool limitations and Persona-Specific Interpretations. This part highlights the initial challenges and inaccuracies encountered using Bard for art interpretation.

- 8) **Results Part A Datasheet:** this document contains the qualitative analysis of Bard's interpretations conducted with all four artworks from earlier experiments using previous Bard version. It includes columns detailing the various figurative elements of each artwork and rows for each persona used in the interpretations. For each iteration of Bard's interpretation, the document reports the meaning Bard assigned to those figurative elements based on the specific persona.
- 9) **Results Part B Datasheet:** this document contains the qualitative analysis of Bard's interpretations conducted with all four artworks from earlier experiments using updated Bard tool. It includes columns detailing the various figurative elements of each artwork and rows for each persona used in the interpretations. For each iteration of Bard's interpretation, the document reports the meaning Bard assigned to those figurative elements based on the specific persona.
- 10) **La Reunion Updated:** This document provides interpretations of the "La Reunion" artwork by Zanele Muholi. It details multiple interactions where Bard was prompted to describe and interpret the image. The document highlights initial misunderstandings by Bard and subsequent corrections, showcasing the AI's learning process. It emphasizes the themes of identity, self-affirmation, and the experiences of black queer individuals.
- 11) **Margaret Thatcher Updated:** this document contains Updated Bard's persona interpretations of "Margaret Thatcher's Lunch" by Derek Jarman. The responses explore various themes such as political critique, the impact of Thatcher's policies on different communities, and personal reflections based on the personas. Bard's interpretations include detailed symbolic meanings of the elements in the artwork.
- 12) **Miss Muffet Updated:** this document details Updated Bard's persona interpretations of the "Little Miss Muffet" artwork by Paula Rego. It includes several iterations of prompts and responses. The document explores the dark and disturbing themes of the artwork.
- 13) **Margaret Thatcher Updated:** this document details Updated Bard's persona interpretations and personal reflections based on the personas. Bard's responses include detailed symbolic interpretations of the elements in the artwork.
- 14) **Differences.docx:** this document details the differences between the earlier experiment and the subsequent tests conducted in the study, focusing on the attributes used for personas. It deals also with detailed considerations about the broadening of features from the earlier investigation and the subsequent experiments.
- 15) **Diversity Test 205 Iterations:** this document provides a comprehensive analysis of Bard's interpretations of Alice Maher's "Berry Dress" from the perspectives of various personas as stated in the major experiment phase. Each interpretation is tailored to reflect the cultural heritage, resilience, strength, and individuality of different personas. The document includes

interpretations from the perspectives of Hispanic, Middle Eastern, African American, and transgender individuals, highlighting how each persona's background and experiences influence the meaning assigned to the artwork. It demonstrates Bard's ability to adapt its interpretations based on detailed persona inputs.

16) Diversity Test Analysis Datasheet: this document reports the results from the major experiment. The quantitative analysis is conducted capturing information about the interpretation for each pair of diversity features used. So, each interpretation generated by the LLM were systematically documented and categorized based on the diversity features emphasized in the responses. The initial dataset consists of the collected interpretations.

17) Decision Tree: a decision tree classifier, generating a hierarchy of priorities between features based on the data of Diversity test analysis. The One-Hot Encoding technique in scikit-learn Python. The code to generate the decision tree is in diversity-classifier2.py. This code first turns the diversity attributes into binary data which is in data2.txt. The .log and .png files show the decision tree output in text and graphical form.

Text References

- **2. Persona-based art interpretations**

- Table 1: Categories and related features, refers to persona used both in the Initial Experiment Phase and in the subsequent experiments. See more in “Differences” file, explaining the reason of persona feature ampliation.
- Initial Experiment Phase: files of the actual interpretation process and thematic categories into each of the artwork document (i.e. Miss Muffet Checked). The version of artwork updated refers to the interpretation results repeated after Bard update in July 2023. In Results document is it possible to view output from interpretation and their qualitative analysis, and reporting of all results by category.
- Example of Impersonating persona prompt from Miss Muffet Checked. More examples can be found in the relevant files for each artwork utilized.
- Example of Targeting Persona Prompts from Berry Dress Checked. More examples can be found in the relevant files for each artwork utilized.
- Overview of Persona designed in a preliminary investigation: see “Persona creation” for the personas used in the art interpretation process.
- Thematic analysis cited in Section 2, can be seen in Results Part A Datasheet (for results before Bard update of Jly 2023 and Results Part B Datasheet (for results of interpretations conducted after Bard update)
- Main points from "Little Miss Muffet" analysis in Section 2 page 6, can be found in Results Part B Datasheet for Miss Muffet interpretation.

- Main points and limitation from "Sthombe La Reunion" interpretation in Section 2 page 6, can be found in Results Part A and Part B Datasheet.
- Main points from "Berry Dress" interpretation in Section 2 page 7, can be found in Results Part A and Part B Datasheet.
- Main points from "Margaret Thatcher's Lunch" interpretation in Section 2 page 7, can be found in Results Part A and Part B Datasheet.
- Summary of preliminary findings: Full results are available in Results Part A and B Documents.

- **Experiment**

- Features design, Page 9, See more in "Differences" file, explaining the reason of persona feature ampliation.
- Artwork selection, Page 9, results cited and more details available at Results Part A and Part B Datasheet.
- Persona generation - Data annotation, Page 9-10, see experiment details in Diversity Test Analysis Datasheet and Diversity Test Iterations document.
- Decision Tree, Page 10 and ss, see Decision tree folder.

- **Discussion**

- Details and results for the discussion, Page 12 and ss, can be read at Results documents and Diversity Test Analysis Datasheet. Decision Tree software can be found in the Decision tree folder.